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Research Article

Effect of Tip Clearance on the Casing over the Impeller on a Low Speed Centrifugal Compressor

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Abstract: The centrifugal compressor is to study the effect of tip clearance on the performance characteristics and the wall static pressure for a different flow coefficient. The tip clearance is varied by using spacers. The volume flow rate is varied with the help of throttling device to conduct the performance test. Obtaining the performance characteristics showing the variation of discharge pressure with volume flow rate for different tip clearance, viz. $\tau = 2.2\%$, 4%, 6.1% and 7.9%. Measurement of periodic pressure at various tip clearance viz. $\tau = 2.2\%$, 4%, 6.1% and 7.9%. For each tip clearance pressure measured in radial location of impeller at 6 positions for five flow coefficients viz., $\phi = 0.40$, $=0.34$ (both the above design flow), $=0.28$ (near design flow), $=0.21=0.18$ (both below design flow) and four values of non dimensional tip clearance viz., $\tau = 2.2\%$, 4%, 6.1% and 7.9%, are chosen for experimental work. The objective of the research work is to measure the periodic variation static pressure on the casing over the rotor at different values of tip clearance and flow coefficients. The periodic pressure data is acquired employing the technique called PLEAT. Experiment carried out in a low speed centrifugal compressor with un-shrouded rotor. Six holes are provided on the casing in which adapters are attached, where the transducers are inserted. The pressure transducer measures pressure in terms of voltage. The voltage output is very low. The output voltage is amplified and converted to digital values for further processing of data.

Sample results are presented and interpreted. From the measured static pressure, tip clearance flows can be easily identified.

Keywords: Centrifugal compressor, tip clearance, casing static pressure, fast response pressure transducer compressor, tip clearance, casing, impeller.

INTRODUCTION

The centrifugal compressor is a major type of compressor used in industrial, vehicular and space applications. It has inherent advantages such as high pressure ratio per stage, reasonable efficiency, large surge margin and low cost. A centrifugal compressor is a pressure producing machine which draws fluid into its impeller at a lower radius and due to external work applied to its shaft, discharges the fluid at a larger radius due to centrifugal effects. It is widely used for many applications, because of their low cost, high-pressure ratio, large surge margin and reasonable efficiencies. There are many factors that affect the performance of centrifugal compressor. Some of them are the inlet geometry, flow angles, clearance between impeller blades and stationary shroud, rotational speed, diffuser type and shape of the volute casing. Of these, flow in the tip clearance region is an important factor. A good knowledge of flow pattern along the shroud and in the tip clearance region is necessary for the better design of compressor. One of the means of studying the flow pattern is by measuring the pressure distribution in this region. However pressure at any point on the shroud is not constant. It varies periodically. This periodic variation of pressure can be measured by using proper instrumentation. Tip clearance deteriorates the performance of a turbomachine. Because of tip clearance, the efficiency of the machine decreases and the pressure losses increases. It also alters the flow pattern in the machine. So it is necessary to understand the physics of the phenomena, and use it in the design, to improve the performance of a turbomachine. Although there are many studies on the effect of tip clearance on the performance of centrifugal compressor, the effects are not clearly understood, because of lack of detailed flow information. Hence the present investigation is undertaken. Precisely the physics of the pressure loss due to tip clearance is not well understood.

Objectives: The objective of the paper is to measure the periodic of variation static pressure on the casing over the impeller at different values of tip clearance and flow coefficients. With the availability of these data, it is possible to improve our understanding of tip clearance flow in centrifugal compressor, with the ultimate aim of minimizing losses.

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATIONS

The experimental set up consisted of centrifugal compressor set-up; driven by 5KW motor. The main components of the compressor are the nozzle at the inlet, the suction duct, the impeller, the vane less diffuser formed by the front and the rear walls of the casing and volute casing of circular cross section and a delivery duct with a throttle at its outlet. The D. C. Motor is directly coupled to the shaft carrying the impeller. A brief description of each of the component of the experimental set-up is given below. Numbers in the brackets refers to **Figure.1**. An inlet nozzle and a suction duct were provided at the inlet of the compressor. The purpose of the nozzle [1] at the inlet of the suction duct [2] is to provide uniform flow to the impeller by accelerating it. Besides, the inlet nozzle is used to measure the volume flow through the impeller. An inlet duct of 300 mm diameter and 1300 mm long is provided at the inlet to the centrifugal compressor. Since the inlet duct is long, the flow will settle by the time it approaches the impeller inlet. The front cover of the casing was designed such a way that its inner surface was similar to the shape of impeller blade shroud contour for its extension formed the

front wall of the vaneless diffuser at the exit of the impeller. Six static pressure holes were made along the meridional plane on the inner contour surface of the shroud from the inlet end to the exit end of the diffuser to measure the static pressures. All the tapping was normal to the inner contour of the shroud. An impeller of a centrifugal compressor is the most delicate part to be designed. It is to be ensured that the flow is ideally oriented in the channel passages. The energy transfer from the shaft to the fluid takes place in the rotating impeller. The existing impeller [6] (Sankaran, 1986) is a special kind, designed to consider the effect of the outlet edges of the vanes of a centrifugal impeller on its performance and flow characteristics. The impeller was designed on the power and speed of the available drive motor. The shape number was chosen was 0.1. The impeller is unshrouded one, with an inducer at the entry. The inducer is provided to give a smooth guidance to the flow turning from axial to radial direction inside the inlet region of the impeller. The ratio of the inducer tip diameter to the impeller outer diameter, d_{1t}/d_{2t} , is 0.6 to minimize the frictional losses. The blade inlet angle β_2 at the impeller tip is 35° . The meridional component of velocity is uniform at the inlet of the impeller. It is nearly constant from the inlet to the exit of the impeller. The number of blades used in the impeller is 16. The selection of the number of blades is based on Pfleiderer's equation, which gives the required number corresponding to the impeller geometry. If an excessive number of blades are used, lesser frictional and blockage would be high reducing the efficiency. Also, if lesser number of blades were used there would not have been proper guidance of the fluid in the impeller resulting in high slip and lowering of the work addition to the fluid. With the lesser number of blades, the blade loading would also be higher. The impeller has twisted blades at the exit region. The impeller blade edges have a maximum twist angle of 15° at the hub and shroud ends. This makes the blade angles at the exit of the impeller to uniformly vary from 75° from the hub end to 90° at the mid span and then to 105° at the shroud end. All angles are measured with respect to the tangential direction.

The major geometrical details of the impeller are given below.

Total pressure rise, ΔP :	300 mm WG
Speed of rotation, N:	2000 rpm
Impeller inlet diameter at inducer tip, d_{1t} :	300 mm
Impeller inlet diameter at inducer hub, d_{1h} :	160 mm
Impeller outer diameter, d_2 :	500 mm
Blade angle at exit	
(a) At hub:	75°
(b) At mean section:	90°
(c) At shroud:	105°
Blade angle at inlet inducer hub, β_{1h} :	53°
Blade angle at inducer tip, β_{1t} :	35°
Blade width at the exit, b:	34.7 mm
No. of blades of the impeller, Z:	16

All the angles are with respect to the tangential direction.

The rear cover of the casing called as back [11] shroud forms the hub wall and is attached to the volute casing [10] by means of studs. A minimum clearance between the impeller and the rear cover is provided to minimize the leakage. The cover of the casing is extended to form the back wall of the vane less diffuser. The vaneless diffuser is a simple device consisting of an annulus in which the radial velocity component is reduced by an increase in the area and the tangential velocity by the requirement of constant fluid angular momentum (free vortex). The extended part of the parallel walls of front cover and the rear cover formed vaneless diffuser. The width of vaneless diffuser was kept

same to direct the flow from, impeller to the annular passage without lateral expansion. The function of the volute casing is to collect the air from the vane less diffuser and discharges it to the delivery duct. The volute casing was of circular cross section. The width at entry to the volute casing is also kept the same as that of the vane less diffuser exit width, so that the surfaces at the two sides of the volute at entry forms a continuous portion of the vaneless diffuser. It is firmly fixed to the foundation. The volute casing is designed for a constant angular momentum for the air stream. The cross-section of the volute is circular. It has a base circle of 630 mm diameter, a volute angle of 13° and cut-off angle of 23° . The passage width at the entry to the volute cross-section at the exit is

Figure-1: Meridional view of impeller showing static pressure measurement positions and Schematic diagram of centrifugal compressor setup

S.NO.	1	2	3	4	5	6
$\frac{m}{m_0}$	-0.13	0.00	0.40	0.67	1.00	1.25

200 mm in diameter and is directly connected to a delivery duct of the same diameter through a 90° bend. The delivery duct is 200 mm in diameter and 5 m in length. The throttle cone is fitted at the end of the delivery duct to regulate the volume flow through the impeller. The average delivery pressure is measured through the static pressure tapping provided on delivery duct wall at a distance of about 1 m from the 90° bend following the volute casing. The throttle cone could be moved forward or backward manually inside the delivery duct to regulate the volume flow through the compressor. On the shroud adapters, for the pressure sensor, are provided at twelve different radial locations from inlet, just behind the leading edge, to exit, after the trailing edge of the impeller. The sensor is passed inside a brass holder of 2 mm internal diameter and with external threading (M4). The sensor is glued to this brass holder using Fevikwik. The brass holder is screwed into these adapters at different locations for

pressure measurement. Spacers were used to maintain the tip clearance accurately. Tip clearance is varied by moving the front shroud axially. Thereby the distance between the front and rear cover would alter. Provisions are made on front cover to fix the spacers in position. Four spacers were used for each tip clearance were fixed at 90 degrees. The experimental investigations involve study for four tip clearance .so hence four set of spacers were made. To measure the suction, delivery and wall static pressures along the shroud and scanning box (Furnace Control Model no. FCO 91-3) with a micro manometer (Model FCO12) manufactured by M/s Furness Control Ltd., Bexhill, UK is used. The micro manometer has a sensitive differential pressure measuring device capable of reading air pressures up to ± 1999 mm WG. It would respond to pressure inputs up to 5 kHz. But the time constant potentiometer could be used to dampen response the fluctuating signal. It is useful in damping flow fluctuations. The pressure can be measured to an accuracy of ± 0.1 mmWG. The scanning box contains 20 valves so we can measure up to 20 pressures. The speed of the centrifugal compressor is measured using a non-contact digital type tachometer. The speed measurement is based upon the evaluation of reflecting pulses from the rotating shaft. It has a range of 0-9999 and its accuracy is ± 1 rpm. Tip clearance is varied by moving the shroud axially. Thereby the distance between the hub and shroud would alter.

Instrumentation for Periodic Pressure Measurement:

Figure-1(1): Schematic layout of the pressure measurement instrumentation

Amplifier as discussed already, the voltage from the transducer is very small so it has to be amplified by using an amplifier. I used Ectron Amplifier (563 H). This 563H transducer conditioning amplifier is a wideband, differential dc instrumentation amplifier with built-in transducer conditioning functions. The compact design features good linearity, gain stability for input impedance. The output of the basic amplifier is 10V at 10mA. The amplifier has 2 channels. The first channel is used to amplify the signals from sensor. The second channel is used to attenuate the signals from the tachometer. On the front panel of the amplifier, rotary gain switch, venire gain control, RTI-zero, RTO-zero, bridge balance potentiometer are provided. On the back panel are TS101, TS102 each consisting ten terminals. The zero detector switch provided on the back panel is moved to off position. The signal generator is used generate a signal of known frequency and amplitude. This is connected to the analogue-to-digital converter. The signal is sampled at known frequency and then converted to digital value. It is stored in a memory location of a personnel computer, from which are signal is plotted. This is compared with original signal.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

The results of experiments conducted on the centrifugal impeller at four values of tip clearances i.e., =2.2%, 4%, 6.1% and 7.9% for four different flow coefficients i.e., = 0.18, 0.21, 0.28, 0.34 and 0.40 are presented and discussed in this chapter. The performance characteristics of the impeller are presented first and then results of wall static pressure measured from the front shroud to impeller exit

are presented.

The result of the experimental investigations revealed that, as the tip clearance is increased, there is a reduction in energy coefficient. The decrease in energy coefficient is more for higher flow coefficient. The operating range also slightly decreases with the increase in the tip clearance (**Figure-2**). The decrease in energy coefficient is higher flow coefficient. The operating range also slightly decreases with the increase in the tip clearance. Using the micro manometer the static pressure difference between the entry and exit of the compressor is measured, at a particular tip clearance. The figure depicts a negligible difference in efficiency for flow coefficients up to 0.30, for all tip clearances. At flow rates higher than this, the difference in efficiency is appreciable, the peak efficiency being lower for higher tip clearance and vice versa. This can be attributed to the increase in tip losses with the increase in the clearance. The reduction in efficiency is due to the reduction in energy transfer for higher tip clearances, since the input power remains more or less the same.

Figure-2: Performance characteristics

The pressure initially decreases due to suction and then uniformly increases, indicating that there are no dead zones or eddies near the shroud region inside the impeller and energy transfer occurs smoothly to the fluid near the shroud (**Figure-3**).

Figure-3: Variation of time averaged static pressure along the casing

The performance of the compressor in terms of energy coefficient vs. flow coefficient is presented in **Figure-2**. The range of flow coefficient for which the compressor operates stably is $\phi=0.08$ to $\phi=0.48$. The result of the experimental investigations revealed that, energy coefficient across the compressor is reduced as the tip clearance is increased. The flow coefficient, where the energy coefficient is maximum decreases with the increase in tip clearance. However the operating range of the compressor is decreased slightly as the maximum volume flow passing through the compressor is reduced with tip clearance. The performance curves shown include losses not only the in the impeller, but also in the following vaneless diffuser, volute casing and delivery duct.

The static pressure distribution measured at the casing static pressure holes, at 2.2% tip clearance for different flow coefficients. On the shroud, static pressure taps were provided from the inducer leading edge to the impeller exit. The shroud has its inner shape contoured to match the impeller blade tip profile from the inlet to the exit. The static pressure measurements on the shroud indicate variation in the static pressure coefficient, which matches with the blade passage clearly. From the figure it is seen that the distribution is high for $\phi=0.28$, as it is nearer to design point operation. The pressure initially decreases due to suction and then uniformly increases,

The local distribution of the casing static pressure is used to draw contours. Such contours at $\phi=0.34$ are shown in **Figure-5 (11)** for four values of tip clearance. Gradual increases of pressure are observed from this meridional distance 0.40 to 0.53. After this meridional distance there is increase in curvature of the casing. Because of this flow accelerates due to which velocity increases and pressure decreases. This decrease in pressure can be clearly observed.

After the meridional distance of 67 percent is reached the curvature straightens up. There is a increase in pressure. This effect can be seen from the figure. The constant pressure lines are sloping towards the suction side of the blade up to meridional distance of 120 percent. After meridional distance of 120 percent which falls in the vane less diffuser section, the slope of the constant pressure lines is almost zero, i.e., the static pressure remains nearly constant in circumferential direction.

UNSTEADY WALL STATIC PRESSURE DISTRIBUTION

The variations of pressure at the **location 1**, the pressure is below atmospheric, which is due to suction. The signals showed a more negative static pressure, compared to that with a flow coefficient of 0.21. But the trend observed in the static pressure between the different tip clearances is the same, for all the above flow coefficients. The suction pressure increases from 0.28 to 0.34 and the effect of tip clearance is predominant as compared to the previous low flow coefficients. For a flow coefficient of 0.40, the suction pressure here also reduces more predominant when tip clearance is increased from 2.2 to 7.9%. The variation of pressure at **location 2**, for a flow coefficient of 0.18. The suction side pressure is below atmospheric, while on the pressure side it is above atmospheric pressure. Though irregularity of pressure variation is present, blade crossing can be observed. Fluid pressure rise is still below atmospheric. The pressure difference between the suction side and pressure side is about 18mmWG. This is because there is not much blade loading at this location. When the tip clearance is increased from 2.2% to 7.9% the maximum pressure is reduced, even the variation is small i.e. maximum of 4mmWG. The variation of pressure at **location 2**, for a flow coefficient of 0.21. The pressure variation for the other flow coefficients was observed. The difference of peak pressures at 2.2% and at 7.9% tip clearance is more when compared to that of at a flow coefficient of 0.18. This pressure difference increases with increased flow coefficient. The pressure fluctuations at **location 3**, for a flow coefficient of 0.18. Periodicity in pressure fluctuations can be seen clearly. Tip clearance effect, i.e. sharp rise and fall in pressure can be seen clearly at minimum pressure position. Similar

trend is observed for the other flow coefficients. The pressure fluctuations **at location 4** for a flow coefficient of 0.18. Clear smooth periodicity of pressure fluctuations is observed on the shroud. Blade positions can be seen clearly. Pressure difference between the suction side and the pressure side of the blade is increased to 80mmWG. Here when the tip clearance is increase the maximum pressure reduces. Maximum pressure difference between 2.2% tip clearance and 7.9% tip clearance is around 25 mm WG only. Similar trend is observed for flow coefficients from 0.21 to 0.40. The average instantaneous pressure values at **5th location** for a flow coefficient of 0.18. It is situated at the exit of the impeller. Similar trend is observed for this location also what we discussed earlier locations. The pressure fluctuations **at 6th location** for a flow coefficient of 0.18. Uniformity in pressure can be seen to certain extent. The pressure difference got diffused due to mixing. Reduction in the intensity of wake is observed. The average pressure is about 160 mm WG for 2.2% tip clearance. It reduces to 150 mm WG when tip clearance increases to 7.9%. The similar trend observed for other flow coefficients 0.21 to 0.40.

Figure-4: Compressor characteristic curve

The static pressure is high for lower tip clearance when compared with that for the higher tip clearance for all flow coefficients. For high flow coefficient, reduction in static pressure is more near the inducer when compared to low flow coefficient, which indicates more deceleration of flow at high flow coefficients (**Figure-5 (1) to 5 (10)**).

Figure-5 (1): Pressure distribution for 1st hole for $\phi = 0.18$

Figure-5 (2) Pressure distribution for 3rd hole for $\phi = 0.21$

Figure-5 (3): Pressure distribution for 3rd hole for $\phi = 0.28$

Figure-5(4): Pressure distribution for 5th hole for $\phi = 0.21$

Figure-5 (5): Pressure distribution for 5th hole for $\phi = 0.28$

Figure-5 (6): Pressure distribution for 5th hole for $\phi = 0.34$

Figure-5 (7): Pressure distribution for 5th hole for $\phi = 0.40$

Figure-5 (8): Pressure distribution for 6th hole for $\phi=0.28$

Figure-5 (9): Pressure distribution for 6th hole for $\phi=0.34$

Figure-5 (10): Pressure distribution for 6th hole for $\phi=0.40$

a) =2.2% for $\phi=0.34$

b) =4% for $\phi=0.34$

c) =6.1% for $\phi=0.34$

d) =7.9% for $\phi=0.34$

Figure-5 (11): Contours of static pressure on casing over the impeller.

CONCLUSIONS

The present experimental investigations were conducted to study the effect of tip clearance on the performance and wall static pressure in a centrifugal compressor. Performance tests were conducted at five flow coefficient with four different tip clearances for each flow coefficient. Based on the experimental investigations, following conclusions are drawn

- 1 As the tip clearance is increased, there is a reduction in static pressure rise across the compressor, which causes reduction in energy coefficient.
- 2 The decrease in energy coefficient is more at higher value of flow coefficient.
- 3 The operating range slightly decreases with the increase in tip clearance.

The wall static pressure is high for lower tip clearance for all the flow coefficients. For high flow coefficient, reduction in static pressure is more near the inducer, which indicates more deceleration of flow at higher flow coefficient. The tip clearance is more pronounced at higher flow coefficients. From these graphs it shows that the maximum pressure is achieved for 2.2% tip clearance, as compared to other tip clearance, for all flow coefficients. Similarly for a flow coefficient of 0.28, the static pressure observed is higher than other flow coefficients for all tip clearances.

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